

Optimizing Procurement Performance Through Effective Planning: A Case Study of TANESCO Dar es Salaam

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Abstract:

This study investigates the impact of procurement planning on procurement performance at TANESCO. Despite ongoing efforts by the Tanzanian government to improve procurement systems, inefficiencies persist at the TANESCO Umeme Park office, including issues with substandard goods and services, unmet policy objectives, and poor coordination, which contribute to elevated operational costs. Factors such as inadequate information, planning strategies, capacity building, conflicts of interest, transparency issues, and resource mismanagement further exacerbate these challenges.

Previous research highlights the need for a participatory approach

involving user departments and stakeholders to enhance procurement processes and optimize resource allocation. Utilizing institutional theory, which focuses on the establishment and evolution of social structures, this study examines how procurement planning, staff competencies, supplier relationships, and resource allocation affect procurement outcomes. The literature review underscores the essential role of procurement planning in improving performance. Empirical evidence indicates that effective procurement planning enhances procurement skills and performance in public organizations. The research specifically assesses the influence of market analysis, budget allocation, and risk management on procurement performance at TANESCO. Findings reveal a strong consensus among respondents regarding the importance of these factors. Market analysis is seen as crucial for better supplier selection and improved procurement efficiency, while inadequate planning leads to increased costs and inefficiencies. Effective budget allocation is highlighted as a key determinant of procurement success, although challenges in integrating it with procurement activities persist. Risk assessment practices are valued but require further refinement to address vulnerabilities. Overall, the study emphasizes the need for integrating strategic planning practices into procurement processes to enhance efficiency and achieve better socio-economic outcomes.

Keywords: *Procurement Planning, Procurement Performance, Market Analysis, Budgetary Allocation and Risk Assessment.*

Introduction

Procurement is a fundamental function in any organization, directly influencing overall operational efficiency and financial stability. The ability of an organization to obtain goods and

services at optimal costs, maintain high quality, and adhere to stipulated timelines is crucial for maintaining a competitive edge and ensuring smooth operations. In this context, procurement planning emerges as a pivotal factor that can

significantly enhance procurement performance (Altekar, 2018).

Globally, procurement practices have evolved substantially, with organizations increasingly adopting advanced strategies to optimize their procurement processes. This evolution is driven by technological advancements, the need for greater transparency, and a relentless pursuit of efficiency and cost-effectiveness (Gallego *et al.*, 2020). Across various sectors, companies are leveraging data analytics and digital platforms to enhance their procurement planning and execution, leading to improved supplier relationships, better contract management, and reduced procurement cycle times.

In Africa, procurement functions play a vital role in economic development by facilitating efficient operations in both public and private sectors. Effective procurement planning in the region is essential for navigating market volatility, budgetary constraints, and unique regulatory environments (Muatwa & Shale, 2023). By adopting best practices in procurement, African organizations can improve resource allocation, mitigate risks, and contribute to sustainable development.

Focusing on Tanzania, the Tanzania Electric Supply Company Limited serves as a critical case study for examining procurement performance due to effective Planning. As the principal electricity generation, transmission, and Distribution Company, TANESCO's procurement strategies have a profound impact on the country's energy sector and, consequently, its economic progress. Effective procurement planning involves rigorous market analysis, prudent budgetary allocation, and comprehensive risk assessment to ensure the availability of resources and services required for uninterrupted power supply.

This paper aims to explore the relationship between procurement planning and procurement performance, focusing on key elements such as market analysis, budgetary allocation, and risk assessment. By examining the processes and practices of procurement planning, particularly in this context, the study seeks to identify best practices and strategies that

can be employed to optimize procurement performance. The conceptual framework guiding this research emphasizes the integration of these elements to enhance efficiency and effectiveness in procurement operations (Shalle *et al.*, 2014).

The study provides valuable insights for procurement professionals and organizational leaders in Tanzania and beyond, highlighting the importance of strategic planning in procurement. By showcasing the role of effective procurement planning in achieving organizational goals and enhancing overall operational efficiency, this paper contributes to the broader discourse on procurement optimization in the global, African, and Tanzanian contexts (Kutata & Noor, 2021).

The main objective of this paper is to examine the influence of Procurement planning on the efficiency of procurement performance.

Significance of this paper is that it examines the critical role of procurement planning in optimizing procurement performance. By focusing on market analysis, budgetary allocation, and risk assessment, the study offers valuable insights into how strategic planning can enhance procurement efficiency and effectiveness. The findings will inform procurement professionals and organizational leaders on best practices, contributing to improved resource management and operational efficiency within TANESCO and similar organizations. This research also adds to the broader understanding of procurement optimization in both African and global contexts.

Significance to the Organization, this research will provide actionable insights into how effective procurement planning, particularly through market analysis, budgetary allocation, and risk assessment, can significantly enhance procurement efficiency and effectiveness. By implementing the findings, Organization can optimize its procurement processes, leading to cost savings, improved resource management, and more reliable power supply, ultimately contributing to the organization's overall operational success.

Significance to the Other Researchers, the study offers a valuable addition to the existing body of knowledge on procurement performance, particularly within the context of public utility companies in Africa. It serves as a foundation for further research on procurement optimization strategies, providing data, methodologies, and conceptual frameworks that can be adapted or expanded in future studies.

Significance to the Policy Makers, the findings of this research can guide policy makers in developing and refining procurement regulations and guidelines, ensuring that procurement practices within public and private sectors align with best practices. By understanding the impact of strategic procurement planning, policy makers can foster more effective and transparent procurement systems, leading to better governance and economic stability.

Significance to the Professionals, Procurement professionals and managers can benefit from the practical recommendations derived from this study. It will equip them with knowledge on optimizing procurement performance through strategic planning, enabling them to make informed decisions, manage risks effectively, and improve overall procurement outcomes within their organizations.

In the context of this study, market analysis refers to the systematic process of gathering, analyzing, and interpreting information about the market in which the entity operates. This includes evaluating the supply market, understanding the availability and prices of goods and services, identifying potential suppliers, assessing market trends, and analyzing the competitive landscape. The objective of market analysis in procurement planning is to make informed decisions that optimize procurement performance by ensuring that the organization secures the best value for money, meets quality standards, and adheres to timelines (Day, 1981).

Budgetary allocation refers to the process of assigning financial resources to different procurement activities within the entity. This involves determining the amount of money that

will be spent on procuring goods and services, considering both current and future needs. In the context of this study, budgetary allocation is critical to procurement performance as it ensures that sufficient funds are available to meet procurement demands while avoiding overspending or underfunding, which can negatively impact operational efficiency and project timelines (Vela, 2023).

Risk assessment in the context of this study involves identifying, analyzing, and evaluating potential risks that could affect PE's procurement activities. This includes considering factors such as supplier reliability, market volatility, legal and regulatory compliance, and logistical challenges. The goal of risk assessment is to mitigate potential disruptions, manage uncertainties, and develop contingency plans to ensure that procurement processes run smoothly, thereby enhancing overall procurement performance (Stephen, 2021).

This paper presents background of the problem, statement of the problem, specific objectives, hypothesis, and significance of research paper, scope, and review of the literature, methodology, findings, discussions, conclusion and recommendation.

Literature Review

Procurement performance is a critical determinant of organizational success, influencing both operational efficiency and strategic outcomes (Onyango, 2012). Effective procurement planning stands at the forefront of optimizing this performance, serving as a foundation for successful procurement activities. As organizations face increasing complexity and competitive pressures, the need to enhance procurement processes through strategic planning has gained prominence (Musau, 2021). This literature review explores the relationship between procurement planning and performance, examining key theories, methodologies, and empirical findings that illuminate how effective planning can drive improvements in procurement outcomes.

The landscape of procurement has evolved significantly over recent decades, driven by advancements in technology, shifts in market dynamics, and growing expectations for sustainability and efficiency (Mwangi, 2020). Effective procurement planning has emerged as a pivotal factor in addressing these changes, enabling organizations to align their procurement strategies with broader business objectives. By systematically evaluating relevant literature, this review aims to provide a comprehensive understanding of the impact of planning on procurement performance, identifying best practices and critical success factors that contribute to optimizing procurement processes (Mujemula, 2019).

This review synthesizes findings from various studies, ranging from theoretical frameworks to empirical research, to highlight the importance of effective planning in procurement (Trochim, 2021). It examines how planning practices influence procurement efficiency, cost management, supplier relationships, and overall organizational performance. Additionally, the review addresses the challenges and limitations associated with procurement planning and offers insights into potential areas for future research. Through this exploration, the review seeks to offer valuable perspectives for practitioners and researchers alike, contributing to the ongoing discourse on enhancing procurement performance through strategic planning.

Theoretical Framework

Institutional theory, as articulated by William Richard Scott (1995), provides a valuable lens for understanding how social structures, including practices and rules, become established as authoritative guidelines influencing behavior. In the context of optimizing procurement performance through effective planning, institutional theory helps elucidate how procurement processes and practices evolve and become standardized within organizations.

Scott's framework emphasizes that institutions are enduring social structures that acquire resilience over time. These structures encompass various components such as schemas, rules, norms, and routines that shape and guide social

behavior. Institutional theory offers insight into how these elements are created, disseminated, and adopted, as well as how they adapt or fall into decline over time.

In the realm of procurement, Kiromo (2021) expands on institutional theory by highlighting that institutions are composed of cultural, cognitive, and regulative elements. These pillars, along with their associated activities and resources, provide meaning and structure to procurement practices. Effective procurement planning can be seen as a response to these institutional pressures, utilizing rules, regulations, and enforcement mechanisms to ensure compliance and enhance performance.

The application of institutional theory to procurement planning underscores the importance of understanding how procurement practices are influenced by institutional norms and expectations. It sheds light on how organizations align their procurement strategies with established norms and regulatory frameworks, and how these practices contribute to optimizing procurement performance. By analyzing procurement performance through the lens of institutional theory, this study aims to explore how effective planning practices can be institutionalized to achieve better procurement outcomes.

Various Studies on the Influence of Procurement Planning on Procurement Performance

Changalima and Mdee (2023) investigated the mediating role of procurement planning between procurement skills and procurement performance in public organizations. Their research underscores the critical importance of procurement planning, demonstrating that effective planning significantly enhances the impact of procurement skills on overall procurement performance. This highlights procurement planning as a crucial factor in optimizing performance outcomes.

In contrast, Kiage (2013) conducted a study within the Ministry of Energy, focusing on procurement performance without directly addressing procurement planning. However, Kiage's findings provided valuable insights into

various factors influencing procurement performance, which could interact with procurement planning to affect overall performance.

Kiplel and Keitany (2018) examined the impact of procurement planning on supplier performance in public institutions, using MOI University as a case study. Their research illustrated that effective procurement planning is essential for cultivating positive supplier relationships, which, in turn, contributes to improved procurement performance. This study highlights how planning can directly influence supplier interactions and performance outcomes.

Lawrence et al. (2020) assessed the effects of procurement planning processes on the performance of construction contracts in local governments in Uganda. Their study found that procurement planning significantly affects contract performance, noting that poor performance was linked to issues such as resource allocation, budget deficits, and unclear procurement requirements. Their results indicate a positive relationship between effective procurement planning and enhanced institutional performance outcomes.

Odero and Ayub (2017) did not directly address procurement planning but explored broader procurement practices impacting performance. Their findings emphasize the need to consider various aspects of procurement management, including planning, to improve performance outcomes.

Nzau and Njeru (2014) investigated factors influencing procurement performance in public universities in Nairobi County. While their focus was not specifically on procurement planning, their study offered valuable insights into the broader context of procurement management, highlighting the relevance of contextual factors in shaping procurement performance.

Mwandobo (2019) conducted a study titled the Role of Procurement Processes on the Effectiveness of Public Procurement System in Tanzania, addressing ongoing issues in the public procurement process, such as delays and substandard delivery. Mwandobo's research, which involved procuring entities in Dar es Salaam, emphasized the need to scrutinize procurement processes and their impact on system effectiveness. This study utilized an explanatory research design with structured questionnaires and interviews, gathering data from 119 out of 155 expected respondents.

The reviewed literature collectively underscores the pivotal role of procurement planning in optimizing procurement performance. Despite variations in focus and methodology, these studies highlight the essential contribution of effective planning practices to enhancing procurement outcomes. Future research should continue to explore the mechanisms underlying the impact of procurement planning on performance and develop strategies for refining planning practices in procurement management.

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework
 Source: Extract from a Researcher own constructs (2024)

Figure 1 illustrates the link between Effective Planning (independent variable) and Procurement Performance (dependent variable). Effective Planning involves strategic alignment, resource allocation, risk management, and process optimization. This structured approach enhances Procurement Performance by improving cost efficiency, timeliness, quality, and supplier relationships. The framework posits that effective planning directly influences procurement outcomes, suggesting that optimized planning practices lead to better overall performance in procurement activities.

Research Methodology

The study employs the Positivist research paradigm, emphasizing quantitative methods, controlled experiments, and statistical analysis to explore cause-and-effect relationships (Mgani, 2021). This approach is well-suited for systematically gathering and analysing numerical data to evaluate how specific factors impact procurement efficiency (Creswell & Creswell, 2017).

A descriptive research design was adopted, aligning with quantitative approaches to analyze numerical data and identify patterns without manipulating variables (Rassel et al., 2020; Sekaran & Bougie, 2016). The research centers on TANESCO's Umeme Park building in Dar es Salaam, focusing on its procurement processes and large projects over the past three years to identify best practices in a complex project environment.

The study targeted 558 employees at TANESCO. Using Slovin's formula, a sample size of 233 respondents was calculated to ensure reliable and generalizable results (Slovin, 1967). Stratified random sampling was used to ensure a representative sample from various organizational levels (Kombo & Tromp, 2006).

Data collection was conducted through questionnaires, chosen for their efficiency and effectiveness in gathering numerical data (Creswell & Creswell, 2017; Babbie, 2016). Both descriptive and inferential analyses, including correlation and linear regression, were employed to assess the impacts of procurement planning, staff competency, and resource allocation on procurement efficiency.

Table 1. Sample of the Study

Department	(N)	Expected sample		
MD Office	4	$4/558 \times 100$	3	1%
Generation Department	36	$36/558 \times 100$	14	6%
ICT Department	73	$73/558 \times 100$	30	13%
Finance	111	$111/558 \times 100$	50	21%
Procurement Management Unit (PMU)	63	$63/558 \times 100$	26	11%
Human resources Office (HR)	125	$125/558 \times 100$	51	22%
Transport Department	41	$41/558 \times 100$	6	7%
Legal Office	13	$13/558 \times 100$	5	2%
Security Department	3	$3/558 \times 100$	3	1%
Transmission	89	$89/558 \times 100$	37	16%
Total	558		233	100%

Note: Therefore, the sample size for this study is 233 respondents

Source: Researcher modeling (2024)

Findings/Results

This article presents the findings of the study on optimizing procurement performance through

effective planning. The results are derived from a comprehensive analysis of the data collected from employees at TANESCO's Umeme Park

building Dar es Salaam. The primary focus is to reveal how effective planning impacts procurement performance, with specific attention to key factors such as strategic alignment, resource allocation, and risk management.

The findings are organized to provide insights into how different elements of procurement planning contribute to overall procurement efficiency. This includes examining the relationships between procurement planning practices and performance indicators such as cost efficiency, timeliness, quality of procurement, and supplier relationship management. The analysis aims to highlight areas where effective planning has positively influenced procurement outcomes and identify any gaps or challenges that need addressing.

By systematically evaluating the data, this section will offer a detailed understanding of the effectiveness of procurement planning strategies and their role in enhancing procurement performance within the context of TANESCO's operations.

Findings of the Study

The study aimed to assess the impact of procurement planning on procurement performance, focusing on market analysis, budgetary allocation, and risk assessment within TANESCO Dar es Salaam. The results provide insights into how these factors influence procurement efficiency.

Respondents strongly agreed that conducting thorough market analysis before initiating procurement processes leads to better supplier selection and improved performance, with a mean score of 4.6 and a low standard deviation of 0.4. However, there was moderate agreement on the impact of inadequate market analysis, with a mean score of 4.2 and a higher standard deviation of 0.7, indicating some variability in perceptions.

Effective budget allocation was also strongly supported, with a mean of 4.3 and a standard deviation of 0.4, highlighting its role in efficient resource utilization. Unforeseen costs due to poor budget planning were acknowledged as an issue (mean = 4.1, SD = 0.9), suggesting that budget planning impacts procurement efficiency. The importance of considering cost fluctuations and market changes in procurement plans was highly rated (mean = 4.6, SD = 0.3), while integrating budget planning with procurement activities received moderate agreement (mean = 3.4, SD = 0.5).

The role of risk assessment in procurement was emphasized, with strong agreement on its importance in reducing delays and inefficiencies (mean = 4.3, SD = 1.2). However, there was significant variability in responses about the impact of poor risk assessment on procurement vulnerabilities (mean = 3.4, SD = 0.8). Regular updates to risk assessments throughout the procurement cycle were highly valued (mean = 4.4, SD = 1.2), though integrating risk management strategies received moderate support (mean = 3.6, SD = 0.6).

The analysis reveals a generally positive perception of procurement planning's impact on performance, with most respondents rating key aspects as "Good" or "Very Good." Thorough market analysis and accurate data utilization are seen as crucial for enhancing procurement performance, though resource investment in market analysis received mixed feedback. Budgetary allocation was highly rated, but integrating it with procurement activities posed challenges. Risk assessment practices were positively viewed, yet concerns about vulnerability due to inadequate risk management were noted. Overall, while the outlook is favorable, certain areas like resource investment in market analysis and risk assessment practices reveal opportunities for further improvement need further improvement.

Table 2. Descriptive Analysis on Effect of Procurement Planning on Procurement Performance

Statement	Agreement level					N	Mn	Mx	M	SD
	1	2	3	4	5					
Market Analysis	Frequencies						Scores			
Conducting thorough market analysis before initiating procurement processes leads to better supplier selection hence public procurement performs well.	20	6	13	23	168	230	2	5	4.6	0.4
Inadequate market analysis results in higher procurement costs due to a lack of knowledge about available options for high performing public procurement	10	7	6	40	167	230	3	5	4.2	0.7
Utilizing accurate and updated market data during procurement planning significantly improves efficiency lead to cost-effectiveness.	14	8	13	26	169	230	2	5	4.1	0.3
Investing in resources for robust market analysis is essential for achieving optimal Procurement Performance in the long run.	19	10	13	23	165	230	2	5	3.8	0.5
Budgetary Allocation										
Effective procurement planning includes clear and realistic budget allocation for each project, leading to efficient resource utilization.	20	6	13	23	168	230	2	5	4.3	0.4
Unforeseen costs arising from poor budget planning cause delays and inefficiencies in the procurement process.	10	7	6	40	167	230	3	5	4.1	0.9
Procurement plans that consider potential cost fluctuations and market changes contribute to achieving budget targets hence overall procurement performance.	14	8	13	26	169	230	2	5	4.6	0.3
Integrating budget planning with procurement activities from the outset leads to better financial control hence improved procurement performance.	5	6	14	35	170	230	2	5	3.4	0.5
Risk Assessment										
Identifying and mitigating potential risks through comprehensive risk assessment during procurement planning reduces delays hence inefficiencies.	21	5	13	28	163	230	2	5	4.3	1.2
Lack of proper risk assessment leaves the procurement process vulnerable to disruptions hence unforeseen challenges, impacting performance of public procurement	10	7	6	40	167	230	3	5	3.4	0.8
Regularly updating risk assessments throughout the procurement cycle ensures efficient adaptation to changing conditions, ultimately maintains project efficiency.	14	8	13	26	169	230	2	5	4.4	1.2
Integrating risk management strategies into procurement planning is crucial for achieving efficiency hence successful procurement outcomes.	17	10	165	25	13	230	3	5	3.6	0.6

Source: Field Data, 2024

Inferential Statistics

Regression Analysis

In this paper, regression analysis is employed as a key method within inferential statistics to

explore the relationships between predictor variables and procurement performance. This analytical approach is pivotal for understanding how various factors specifically Market Analysis,

Budgetary Allocation, and Risk Assessment impact procurement outcomes. By applying regression analysis, the study aims to quantify the strength and nature of these relationships, providing valuable insights into how these variables contribute to optimizing procurement performance. The results of this analysis will help to identify the most significant predictors of success and guide strategic improvements in procurement practices. Through a detailed examination of the regression model, this section will present findings on the efficacy of different predictors and their implications for enhancing procurement efficiency.

In this study, multiple regression analysis was performed to examine the influence of three predictor variables on the Procurement performance of public procuring entities, as well as to assess the relationship between the independent and dependent variables. The Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS Version 21.0) was utilized to code, enter, and compute the measurements for the multiple regression analysis. The model summary for the regression analysis is presented in Tables 3, 4, and 5.

Model Summary

Table 3. Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.936 ^a	.876	.873	.18130

a. Predictors: (Constant), Market Analysis, Budgetary Allocation, Risk Assessment

Source: Field Data, (2024)

The model summary utilizes the coefficient of determination to assess how well the independent variables explain the dependent variable. The adjusted R² value of 0.873 suggests that 87.3% of the variance in procurement performance can be attributed to the predictors Market Analysis, Budgetary Allocation, and Risk

Assessment indicating a strong model fit. The R value of 0.936 further supports this, demonstrating a significant positive correlation between the predictors and procurement performance. This implies that improvements in these areas are likely to have a substantial impact on enhancing procurement performance.

Table 4. ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	27.552	3	9.184	279.415	.000 ^b
	Residual	3.879	118	.033		
	Total	31.431	121			

a. Dependent Variable: Procurement performance
b. Predictors: (Constant), Market Analysis, Budgetary Allocation, Risk Assessment.

According to Table 4, the regression model is statistically significant, as indicated by a significance level of 0.000, which is well below the critical threshold of 0.05. This result confirms that the independent variables Market Analysis, Budgetary Allocation, and Risk

Assessment are crucial predictors for explaining variations in the dependent variable, procurement performance.

Multiple Regression Analysis Results

Table 5. Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	-.072	.067		-1.060	.014
	Market Analysis	.540	.042	.036	.807	.021
	Budgetary Allocation	.941	.049	.883	19.126	.004
	Risk Assessment	.560	.041	.053	1.363	.035

a. Dependent Variable: Procurement performance

Source: Field Data, (2024)

From the coefficient table 5, the following regression equation was obtained.

$$Y = -0.072 + 0.540X_1 + 0.941X_2 + 0.56X_3 + 0.067$$

Where:

Y= Procurement performance

β_0 = Regression Constant

X1= Market Analysis

X2= Budgetary Allocation

X3= Risk Assessment

ϵ = Error

Table 5 provides the coefficients from the multiple regression analysis examining the impact of Procurement planning as attributed by Market Analysis, Budgetary Allocation, and Risk Assessment on procurement performance. The results are detailed as follows:

The constant value was -0.072 with a standard error of 0.067, a t-value of -1.060, and a significance level of 0.014. Despite the constant being significant, its negative value indicates that, when all other variables are held at zero, the baseline procurement performance is slightly below the reference level. However, in the context of this model, the constant does not significantly contribute to the explanation of procurement performance.

Market Analysis, the coefficient for Market Analysis is 0.540 with a standard error of 0.042, a standardized beta of 0.036, a t-value of 0.807, and a significance level of 0.021. This positive

coefficient suggests a direct relationship between Market Analysis and procurement performance. However, while the coefficient indicates a positive impact, the significance level of 0.021 suggests that Market Analysis has a marginally significant influence on procurement performance. This result implies that, although Market Analysis contributes to procurement performance, its impact may be modest or influenced by other factors not fully captured in this model.

Budgetary Allocation, the coefficient for Budgetary Allocation is 0.941 with a standard error of 0.049, a standardized beta of 0.883, a t-value of 19.126, and a significance level of 0.004. This high coefficient and significant p-value confirm that Budgetary Allocation is a robust predictor of procurement performance. The strong positive relationship indicates that effective and precise budgeting is crucial for optimizing procurement performance. This result aligns with the literature emphasizing the importance of strategic budget planning in enhancing procurement outcomes.

Risk Assessment, the coefficient for Risk Assessment is 0.560 with a standard error of 0.041, a standardized beta of 0.053, a t-value of 1.363, and a significance level of 0.035. The positive coefficient suggests that effective Risk Assessment has a beneficial impact on procurement performance. The significance level of 0.035 indicates that Risk Assessment is a statistically significant predictor, reinforcing the need for comprehensive risk management to reduce procurement disruptions and improve performance.

Overall, the analysis reveals that Budgetary Allocation and Risk Assessment are significant predictors of procurement performance, with Budgetary Allocation showing the strongest impact. Market Analysis, while positive, does not achieve a high level of statistical significance in this model. These findings highlight the critical importance of effective budget planning and risk management in optimizing procurement performance, as outlined in the broader literature on procurement planning and efficiency.

Discussion of Finding

The findings from the study provide valuable insights into the factors that significantly impact procurement performance, emphasizing the roles of Market Analysis, Budgetary Allocation, and Risk Assessment. The analysis highlights both quantitative and qualitative perspectives on how these elements influence procurement outcomes.

The study aimed to assess the impact of procurement planning on procurement performance, with a focus on key elements such as market analysis, budgetary allocation, and risk assessment. The findings provide critical insights into how these factors influence procurement efficiency and overall performance.

The results reveal a strong consensus among respondents on the importance of conducting thorough market analysis before initiating procurement processes. A mean score of 4.6, with a low standard deviation of 0.4, indicates a clear agreement that effective market analysis enhances supplier selection and improves procurement performance. This is consistent with Day's (1981) work, which highlights that a strategic approach to market analysis enables organizations to select the best suppliers, thereby gaining a competitive advantage and improving procurement outcomes.

However, there was moderate agreement regarding the impact of inadequate market analysis, with a mean score of 4.2 and a higher standard deviation of 0.7, suggesting some variability in perceptions. This finding aligns

with Hamza (2016), who noted that gaps in market research can result in inefficient procurement processes. Despite the strong support for market analysis, there appears to be room for improvement, particularly in how resources are allocated to this function.

Effective budgetary allocation was also highly rated by respondents, with a mean of 4.3 and a standard deviation of 0.4, emphasizing its critical role in efficient resource utilization. This supports the findings of Kiage (2013), who identified budget planning as a central factor influencing procurement performance in the public sector. However, unforeseen costs arising from poor budget planning were highlighted as a challenge, with a mean score of 4.1 and a standard deviation of 0.9. These results align with Benjamin (2019), who found that inadequate budgeting and financial planning can lead to cost overruns and inefficiencies in procurement processes.

The need to consider market fluctuations and cost changes during procurement planning was rated highly (mean = 4.6, SD = 0.3). However, there was moderate agreement on the integration of budgetary planning with procurement activities (mean = 3.4, SD = 0.5), indicating a disconnect between planning and execution, which was similarly observed in studies by Kiplel and Keitany (2018). This suggests that while budgetary allocation is critical, there are challenges in aligning it with actual procurement processes.

Risk assessment was found to play a crucial role in improving procurement performance, as respondents strongly agreed that it reduces delays and inefficiencies (mean = 4.3, SD = 1.2). This aligns with Igosangwa (2019), who emphasized the importance of risk management in mitigating potential procurement disruptions in public institutions. Nonetheless, the variability in responses regarding the effects of inadequate risk assessment (mean = 3.4, SD = 0.8) suggests that risk management practices are not consistently applied, leaving room for vulnerability in the procurement process. This finding is echoed by Damas (2021), who noted that weak risk management strategies in public

sector procurement can lead to significant operational inefficiencies.

Regular updates to risk assessments were highly valued by respondents (mean = 4.4, SD = 1.2), reinforcing the need for continuous monitoring and evaluation of risks throughout the procurement cycle. However, the integration of risk management strategies into the overall procurement framework received only moderate support (mean = 3.6, SD = 0.6), pointing to potential gaps in organizational risk management practices.

The regression analysis performed to examine the influence of market analysis, budgetary allocation, and risk assessment on procurement performance demonstrated a strong model fit, with an adjusted R^2 value of 0.873. This suggests that 87.3% of the variance in procurement performance can be explained by the three predictors, indicating their significant contribution to the success of procurement activities. The R value of 0.936 also indicates a high positive correlation between these variables and procurement performance, reinforcing the idea that improvements in market analysis, budgeting, and risk management are likely to have a substantial impact on procurement efficiency.

The results of the ANOVA test further confirm the statistical significance of the model, with a significance level of 0.000, indicating that the independent variables (market analysis, budgetary allocation, and risk assessment) are crucial in explaining procurement performance.

The regression coefficients show that budgetary allocation ($\beta = 0.941$, $p = 0.004$) has the strongest impact on procurement performance, followed by risk assessment ($\beta = 0.560$, $p = 0.035$), and market analysis ($\beta = 0.540$, $p = 0.021$). These findings align with the literature, particularly Benjamin (2019) and Kiromo (2019), who both identified budgetary planning and risk management as key drivers of procurement success.

Overall, the study highlights that procurement planning plays a vital role in optimizing procurement performance, with market analysis, budgetary allocation, and risk assessment all

contributing significantly to procurement outcomes. However, challenges remain in the areas of resource allocation for market analysis, the integration of budgetary planning with procurement activities, and the consistent application of risk management practices. Addressing these issues will be critical for enhancing the overall efficiency and effectiveness of procurement functions at TANESCO, as emphasized by Kasis (2019) and Damas (2021).

Hence, while the outlook for procurement planning at TANESCO is generally positive, there are opportunities for further improvement, particularly in aligning market analysis, budgetary planning, and risk management more closely with procurement execution to achieve optimal performance.

Conclusion

The underscores the pivotal role of strategic planning in improving procurement outcomes. The findings indicate that elements such as Market Analysis, Budgetary Allocation, and Risk Assessment are crucial to enhancing procurement performance. Among these, Budgetary Allocation emerged as the most significant predictor, highlighting the critical role of precise financial planning and resource management in achieving procurement efficiency.

The study highlights TANESCO's strengths, particularly in budget planning, but also identifies areas for improvement in Market Analysis and Risk Assessment. Addressing these gaps could further enhance procurement processes, leading to greater efficiency and effectiveness.

The analysis shows that thorough Market Analysis is associated with better supplier selection and performance, supported by a mean score of 4.6. However, perceptions of inadequate Market Analysis are more variable (mean = 4.2). Effective Budgetary Allocation is also strongly supported (mean = 4.3), though there are concerns about unforeseen costs due to poor budget planning (mean = 4.1). The

integration of budget planning with procurement activities received moderate agreement (mean = 3.4).

Risk Assessment is recognized for its importance in reducing delays and inefficiencies (mean = 4.3), though its impact on vulnerabilities shows significant variability (mean = 3.4). Regular updates to risk assessments are highly valued (mean = 4.4), yet integrating risk management strategies received moderate support (mean = 3.6).

The regression analysis reveals that 87.3% of the variance in procurement performance can be explained by Market Analysis, Budgetary Allocation, and Risk Assessment, indicating a strong model fit. Budgetary Allocation is identified as a highly significant predictor of procurement performance, while Market Analysis and Risk Assessment do not show statistical significance in this model.

Overall, the study concludes that procurement performance at TANESCO can be significantly improved through a holistic planning approach. This involves refining Market Analysis, enhancing Risk Assessment practices, and continuing effective Budgetary Allocation to meet strategic objectives and boost overall efficiency.

Recommendations

To enhance effective Market Analysis practices, TANESCO should allocate more resources to conduct thorough market research before initiating procurement processes, which will improve supplier selection and performance. Developing and implementing standardized procedures for market analysis is essential to ensure consistency and reliability across procurement activities. Additionally, providing training for procurement staff on advanced market analysis techniques and tools will enhance accuracy and effectiveness.

For optimizing Budgetary Allocation, it is crucial to refine budget planning processes to minimize unforeseen costs and incorporate contingency plans to address potential financial uncertainties. Enhancing the integration of budgetary planning

with procurement activities will ensure better alignment and resource utilization. Establishing a system for regular monitoring and adjustment of budgets to accommodate cost fluctuations and market changes is also recommended.

To strengthen Risk Assessment procedures, TANESCO should conduct regular updates and reviews of risk assessments throughout the procurement cycle to address emerging risks and reduce vulnerabilities. Developing and integrating comprehensive risk management strategies into procurement processes will help mitigate potential delays and inefficiencies. Offering training on risk assessment and management techniques for procurement professionals will improve their ability to identify and address risks effectively.

Fostering a holistic planning approach involves implementing an integrated planning framework that combines Market Analysis, Budgetary Allocation, and Risk Assessment to optimize procurement performance. Encouraging cross-functional collaboration between departments involved in procurement will ensure that all critical factors are considered and addressed.

Lastly, monitoring and evaluating performance is crucial. Developing and monitoring key performance indicators (KPIs) will help assess the effectiveness of procurement planning and its impact on procurement performance. Using performance data to identify areas for improvement and implementing continuous improvement initiatives will further enhance procurement processes.

By focusing on these recommendations, TANESCO can significantly enhance its procurement performance, achieve greater efficiency, and better align with its strategic objectives.

References

- Altekar, R. V. (2018). *Supply Chain Management: Ester Economic Edition*. PHI Learning Private Limited.
- Benjamin, E. (2019). Factors affecting the performance of the procurement function in

- government organizations: Moi University, Jomo Kenyatta, and Kirinyaga University. *International Journal of Scientific Engineering and Research (IJSER)*.
- Bryman, A. (2016). *Social research methods*. Oxford University Press.
- Changalima, I. A., & Mdee, A. E. (2023). Procurement skills and procurement performance in public organizations: The mediating role of procurement planning. *Cogent Business & Management*, 10(1), Article 2163562. <https://doi.org/10.1080/23311975.2023.2163562>
- Creswell, J. W., & Creswell, J. D. (2017). *Research design: Qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods approaches*. Sage Publications.
- Damas, M. (2021). Factors affecting procurement functions in the public sector. University of Kenya.
- Day, G. S. (1981). Strategic market analysis and definition: An integrated approach. *Strategic Management Journal*, 2(3), 281-299. <https://doi.org/10.1002/smj.4250020303>
- Hamza, S. B. (2016). Factors affecting procurement performance in the case of Awassa Textile Share Company. *Global Journal of Management and Business Research: G Interdisciplinary*, 16(3).
- Igosangwa, R. A. M. (2019). Factors affecting procurement lead-time and operational performance in state-owned financial institutions in Kenya. University of Nairobi.
- Kasis, U. (2014). Factors affecting the performance of the procurement function in government organizations: Moi University, Jomo Kenyatta, and Kirinyaga University. *International Journal of Scientific Engineering and Research (IJSER)*.
- Kiage, J. O. (2013). Factors affecting procurement performance: A case of Ministry of Energy. *International Journal of Business and Commerce*, 3(1), 54-70.
- Kiplel, M. C., & Keitany, P. (2018). Effect of procurement planning on suppliers' performance in public institutions: A case of Moi University.
- Kiromo, E. M. (2019). Factors affecting procurement and supply chain performance in building construction firms in Nairobi. University of Nairobi.
- Kothari, C. R. (2020). *Research methodology* (2nd ed.). V.S. Johri.
- Muhwezi, L., Musiime, F. T., & Onyutha, C. (2020). Assessment of the effects of procurement planning processes on performance of construction contracts in local governments in Uganda. *Journal of Civil, Construction and Environmental Engineering*, 5(6), 151-160. <https://doi.org/10.11648/j.jccee.20200506.12>
- Mgani, D. (2021). Evaluation of public procurement and performance in Tanzania. Mzumbe University.
- Mrope, N. P. (2017). The effect of professionalism on performance of procurement function in the public sector. *International Journal of Business and Management Review*, 5(6), 48-59.
- Mujemula, S. D. (2019). The challenges facing the procurement department in working organizations in Tanzania. Mzumbe University.
- Musau, E. G. (2021). Environmental factors affecting procurement performance in county governments: A case of Uasin Gishu County. *International Journal of Business and Management Invention*.
- Mwandobo, J. C. (2019). The role of procurement processes on the effectiveness of the public procurement system in Tanzania. Mzumbe University.
- Mwangi, K. (2020). Factors affecting the performance of the procurement function in government organizations: Moi University, Jomo Kenyatta, and Kirinyaga University. *International Journal of Scientific Engineering and Research (IJSER)*.
- Nzau, A., & Njeru, A. (2014). Factors affecting procurement performance of public universities in Nairobi County. *International Journal of Social*

Sciences and Project Planning Management, 1(3), 147-156.

Odero, J. A., & Ayub, S. E. (2017). Effect of procurement practices on procurement performance of public sugar manufacturing firms in Western Kenya. *International Journal of Management Research and Reviews*, 7(4), 521.

Okinyi, T. O. (2019). Factors affecting efficiency of procurement in public institutions: Jomo Kenyatta University of Agriculture and Technology. *Journal of Social Science and Information Technology*, 2(2).

Onyango, C. J. (2012). Effects of procurement planning on institutional performance: A case study of Mombasa Law Court. *International Journal of Science and Research (IJSR)*, 3(11), 446-455.

Saunders, L. (2019). *Research methods for business students* (4th ed.). Pearson Education.

Sekaran, U. (2003). *Research methods for business*. John Wiley & Sons.

Sekaran, U. (2006). *Research methods for business: A skill-building approach* (4th ed.). AR MM International.

Sekaran, U., & Bougie, R. (2016). *Research methods for business: A skill-building approach*. John Wiley & Sons.

Stephen, C. (2021). Factors hindering performance of procurement. Mzumbe University.

Tanzania Electric Supply Company Limited. (2023). [<https://www.tanESCO.co.tz/>]

Trochim, W. (2021). *The research methods knowledge base* (2nd ed.). Web Center for Social Research Methods.

Vela, R. (2023). Procurement performance: Maximizing efficiency and value in supply.

Wabala, S. (2021). Influence of procurement planning on the procurement performance of selected county governments in Kenya. *International Research Journal of Business and Strategic Management*.

Wanyonyi, S. C. (2021). Factors affecting performance of procurement function among public technical training institutions in Kisumu County, Kenya. *International Journal of Economics, Commerce and Management (UK)*.